

**ROSSIYA IMPERIYASINING TURKISTONDAGI IQTISODIY SIYOSATI:
ASOSIY YO‘NALISHLARI VA RIVOJLANISHI****Abdimurodov Shahboz Davron o‘g‘li**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada XIX asr oxiri va XX asr boshlarida Rossiya imperiyasining Turkistondagi iqtisodiy siyosati tahlil qilinadi. Alohida e‘tibor yer va suv islohotlari, soliq siyosati, transport infratuzilmasi, savdo va sanoatni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan. Maqolada shuningdek, Turkistonning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy hayoti uchun imperiya iqtisodiy siyosatining ijobiy va salbiy oqibatlarini baholanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Rossiya imperiyasi, Turkiston, iqtisodiy siyosat, soliqqa tortish, yer islohoti, temir yo‘llar, sanoat, mustamlakachilik.

**ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКАЯ ПОЛИТИКА РОССИЙСКОЙ ИМПЕРИИ В
ТУРКЕСТАНЕ: ОСНОВНЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ И РАЗВИТИЕ****Абдимуродов Шахбоз Даврон оглы**

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Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется экономическая политика Российской империи в Туркестане в конце XIX и начале XX веков. Особое внимание уделяется земельной и водной реформам, налоговой политике, транспортной инфраструктуре и торгово-промышленному развитию. В статье также оцениваются положительные и отрицательные последствия имперской экономической политики для социально-экономической жизни Туркестана.

Ключевые слова: Российская империя, Туркестан, экономическая политика, налогообложение, земельная реформа, железная дорога, промышленность, колониализм.

**ECONOMIC POLICY OF THE RUSSIAN EMPIRE IN TURKESTAN: MAIN
DIRECTIONS AND DEVELOPMENT****Abdimurodov Shahboz Davron ugli**

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Abstract: This article analyzes the economic policy pursued by the Russian Empire in Turkestan during the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. Special attention is given to land and water reforms, taxation policy, transport infrastructure, and trade-industrial development. The article also evaluates the positive and negative consequences of imperial economic policy for the social and economic life of Turkestan.

Key words: Russian Empire, Turkestan, economic policy, taxation, land reform, railway, industry, colonialism.

Introduction. In the second half of the 19th century, the Russian Empire conquered Central Asia, particularly Turkestan, and introduced a colonial system of governance in the region. One of the most important directions of the empire's policy was to reshape the local economy in accordance with Russian interests. The Russian administration aimed to include Turkestan in the

economic system of the empire as a region supplying raw materials and a ready market for industrial products. For this reason, large-scale economic changes were carried out in the country's agriculture, trade, transport, and financial systems. This study analyzes in detail the main directions of the economic policy of the Russian Empire in Turkestan, the mechanisms for its implementation, and the consequences of this policy for local society and economy.

Literature analysis and methodology. The study was conducted based on historical-analytical methodology. The main sources were scientific articles, monographs, official statistical collections, and historical literature created by Uzbek and Russian scientists. During the study, comparative and descriptive approaches were used to study the economic reforms of the Russian Empire in Turkestan and their impact on the life of local society. Also, in order to determine the long-term results of economic policy, the sequence of historical processes and stages of development were consistently analyzed. The chronological scope of the study mainly covers the late 19th and early 20th centuries. It was this period that was considered the period when the economic policy of the Russian Empire in Turkestan was most actively implemented and the colonial economic system was fully formed.

Results and discussion. The Russian Empire implemented a number of major economic policies in Turkestan. The main goal of these policies was to completely subordinate the country to the imperial economic system and turn it into a raw material base for Russian industry. First of all, the reorganization of land and water relations became an important component of colonial policy. In accordance with the "Regulations on the Management of the Turkestan Territory" adopted in 1886, land was declared state property and the hereditary lands of the local population were reclassified. As a result, many fertile territories were given to representatives of the population relocated from Russia. In particular, Russian peasants from Saratov, Astrakhan and other provinces were actively settled in Turkestan. The relocation of more than 500 thousand Russian settlers to Turkestan between 1906 and 1916 sharply increased the shortage of land among local peasants. As a result of the reduction of irrigated land, the economic situation of the local population worsened.

The second important direction was related to the tax system. The Russian Empire introduced various taxes and compulsory labor obligations in order to make the population of Turkestan economically dependent on the center. The amount of taxes imposed on the local population was increased, and customs duties had a negative impact on the development of internal trade and entrepreneurship. As a result of tax pressure, many artisans and small traders faced economic difficulties. Thus, the possibilities for independent development of the local economy were limited.

The development of the transport and infrastructure system also acquired strategic importance for the Russian Empire. The construction of the Trans-Caspian Railway and the Tashkent-Orenburg Railway connected Turkestan with the industrial centers of Russia. Cotton, wool, leather and other raw materials were transported to Russia via these railways. At the same time, the railways also served military and political purposes. They made it possible to quickly deploy troops and strengthen colonial rule. As a result, Russia's political and military control over the region was further strengthened.

Trade and industrial policy also served mainly Russian interests. Cotton ginning factories, metal workshops, and various industrial enterprises were established in Turkestan mainly at the expense of Russian capital. However, these enterprises were oriented more towards the interests of imperial industry than local economic needs. Cheap industrial products imported from Russia reduced the competitiveness of local crafts and traditional production sectors. As a result, many craftsmen lost their sources of livelihood and were forced to become hired workers.

Although the Russian Empire introduced new economic relations and infrastructure in Turkestan, the reforms carried out mainly served colonial interests. Turkestan was transformed into an agrarian and raw material supplying peripheral region of the empire. In particular, cotton

cultivation expanded sharply. As a result, the area of grain crops decreased, food shortages increased, and social instability arose.

This economic policy also led to a deepening of social inequality. While Russian nomads often had tax privileges and fertile land, local peasants were forced to live under increasing economic pressure. Industrial development in Turkestan was mainly limited to primary processing industries. The production of finished products was carried out in the central regions of the empire. This hindered the independent industrial development of the Turkestan economy.

The construction of railways further strengthened Russia's military and political influence in the region. The transport system made it possible to quickly move troops and strengthen administrative control. At the same time, industrial products manufactured in Russia entered local markets widely, weakening traditional crafts and small-scale industries.

As a result, colonial economic policies led to the intensification of social discontent and national liberation movements in Turkestan. The imbalance between the interests of the empire and the needs of the local population seriously hindered the independent economic development of the region. Although the economic policy of the Russian Empire in Turkestan brought significant economic benefits to the empire in the short term, in the long term it had a negative impact on the economic and social development of local society.

The economic policy of the Russian Empire in Turkestan introduced elements of modernization to a certain extent. In particular, the construction of railways, the establishment of industrial enterprises, and the involvement of the region in market relations led to certain changes in the economic system. The development of transport and communication infrastructure served to expand trade relations and led to a deeper integration of Turkestan into the economic system of the Russian Empire. At the same time, the emergence of certain industries and the formation of new economic relations laid the foundation for the development of capitalist relations in the country.

However, the main goal of these reforms was not to ensure the independent development of Turkestan, but to serve the economic and political interests of the empire. The Russian Empire formed Turkestan mainly as a region supplying raw materials and a market for its industrial products. The large-scale exploitation of natural resources, the dominance of Russian capital, and the restriction of local economic initiatives hindered the balanced economic development of the region.

Conclusion. The sharp expansion of cotton cultivation increased one-sided specialization in the structure of agriculture and had a negative impact on food security. Local crafts and traditional production sectors were weakened, unable to compete with cheap industrial products imported from Russia. As a result, many local residents were forced to live in conditions of economic dependence and poverty. Increasing social inequality, land issues and economic pressure intensified the mood of discontent against colonial policies.

Nevertheless, the desire of the peoples of Turkestan for freedom, independence and national development was preserved. The national consciousness and liberation movements formed against colonial oppression later served as an important historical basis in the process of gaining independence for Uzbekistan. Therefore, the study of the economic policy of the Russian Empire in Turkestan is of great importance not only in understanding the economic relations of the colonial period, but also in understanding the subsequent political and social development of the region.

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